

BEST SCIENTISTS 2023 JOURNAL

Remote monitoring of patient health using wireless technologies!

Abdugafur Hotamov

Associate Professor of the Samarkand branch of TUIT named after Muhammad al-Khorazmi

abdugafur.xotamov@gmail.com

Normurodova E'zoza Akbar qizi

Master of the Samarkand branch of TUIT named after Muhammad al-Khorazmi

Annotation

In this article, fundamental improvement of the health care sector, provision of quality medical services to our people, strengthening of reproductive health of the population, protection of motherhood and childhood, creation of necessary conditions for raising a healthy generation are defined as one of the priorities of our state's policy, and unprecedented work has been done in this way. , despite the fact that the medicine of our country has passed a serious test during the pandemic of the coronavirus disease, and despite the fact that all the possibilities of our country have been used to fight against this dangerous disease, prevent its spread among the population, protect our people from this scourge, and protect their health, regular monitoring of the health of the population in remote mountainous areas is important to do.

BEST SCIENTISTS 2023 JOURNAL

Key words: Telemedicine, vaccination, infrastructure, medical aviation, diagnosis, diagnostics.

Main part

In this article, fundamental improvement of the health care sector, provision of quality medical services to our people, strengthening of reproductive health of the population, protection of motherhood and childhood, creation of necessary conditions for raising a healthy generation are defined as one of the priorities of our state's policy, and unprecedented work has been done in this way. , despite the fact that the medicine of our country has passed a serious test during the pandemic of the coronavirus disease, and despite the fact that all the possibilities of our country have been used to fight against this dangerous disease, prevent its spread among the population, protect our people from this scourge, and protect their health, regular monitoring of the health of the population in remote mountainous areas is important to do. Taking into account the hot and dry climatic conditions of the Central Asian region, it is important to regularly monitor the health of the population living in the desert regions of Qizilqum, Karakum and mountainous regions. Today, in such cases, it is necessary to monitor the health of the population using a remote wireless network. Although it is not noticeable to us today, many discovery revolutions have taken place in the world. In the near future, we think they will begin to directly affect us as well. We are talking about health care and remote monitoring of the patient's health based on modern technologies in this field.

Telemedicine is the practice of treating patients remotely

BEST SCIENTISTS 2023 JOURNAL

telecommunications and information technologies. For the patient in return no distance can be a barrier to treatment and patients from medical services can use. It lives in hard-to-reach places provides a convenient opportunity to provide medical advice to the population. Besides in emergency situations, it allows to save the lives of patients in critical condition remotely.

Fields of application of telemedicine technologies today:

- Remote interactive training of doctors;
- Learning new medical technologies and equipment;
- High-tech remote videoconferencing for critically ill patients transfer;
- Providing urgent teleconsultation with the help of mobile and mobile telemedicine complex;

Video communication equipment:

Video calling apps like WebEx and Skype have been hard to come by the best tool for the population in the regions to communicate with medical personnel is considered. Instead of waiting for a medical worker to arrive in remote rural areas this method of medical care can be used immediately, this method has been introduced in many foreign countries.

Diagnostic visualization mobile centers:

Diagnostic centers are complete with X-ray equipment and analysis. In rural areas where it is difficult to equip, mobile diagnostic visualization centers and laboratory-type points will be of great importance in making a real diagnosis by sending the received data to large centers. In general, doctors have this opportunity and can really treat the patient. Specialists of Kaiser Permanente California, a non-

BEST SCIENTISTS 2023 JOURNAL

profit medical organization, use these methods to receive and treat more than 800 patients per month, and 50% more patients than the population in hard-to-reach areas.

Remote check.

Despite the advantages of video communication equipment, the opportunities provided by new technologies cannot replace a doctor in providing rapid first aid in emergency situations, elderly people or chronic disease attacks and other medical situations. For this purpose, new modern devices have been developed, thanks to which patients can regularly monitor their health at home, regardless of where they are.

These devices send the received data to current control centers, where the patient's health status is monitored by doctors. No matter how far the doctor is geographically, he will be able to immediately take the necessary measures and give important instructions for life. This is the best opportunity to support the health of patients. Mahalliy ijtimoiy tuzilmalarning rivojlanishi uchun tibbiy uskunalari: Patients who can help other patients - this is the field of medical care is an excellent approach to expansion. In some cases, patients do not need professional medical assistance, but it is enough to get advice from other patients who have faced similar problems. Online methods of e-communities, such as PatientsLikeMe.com, allow groups of patients to communicate regardless of geographic location without increasing costs, requiring patients to have only a cell phone or computer to access the service. required.

Among those who are effectively using telemedicine equipment on a large scale

BEST SCIENTISTS 2023 JOURNAL

Africa occupies a special place. Virtual Doctors is a not-for-profit medical system designed specifically for rural areas in Africa to provide simple telemedicine software that facilitates communication and diagnosis between a team of dedicated medical professionals and medical experts known as remote medical guides. allows to put and treat.

Telemedicine is becoming more and more popular, in fact, it cannot replace doctors, especially in rural areas, but it is already finding its place in immediate access to medical services and routine health care. It also provides immediate access to medical services in hard-to-reach remote areas. The goal of advanced technologies is always to bridge the gap to convenience, and telemedicine is a great example of this.

1-picture Teleconferencing tools in medicine

BEST SCIENTISTS 2023 JOURNAL

Epidemic using information and communication technologies
situation monitoring and control system

The composition of the mobile telemedicine complex:

1. Sputnik terminal with battery.
2. Video conference communication systems with battery and illumination.
3. Interactive helmet transmitting video/audio (full complex).
4. Medical equipment complex
5. Problem solving system (expert system)

VKS transfer in urgent situations -01.

Home telemedicine - remote patient health monitoring through video
communication to do On the doctor screen:

medical history of the patient;

the result of the last electrocardiography;

video communication between the doctor and the patient is shown

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that the concept of "Telemedicine technologies" should be clarified, the types of medical care that can be used using these technologies, and the list of permitted types of telemedicine activities (council, consultation, remote medical monitoring of the patient's health), development of telecommunication infrastructure, and in this direction, it is necessary to improve the qualification of our doctors.

BEST SCIENTISTS 2023 JOURNAL

As a result of the establishment of the telemedicine service, people in the regions will have the opportunity to directly use qualified and high-quality medical services.

References.

1. Ulla S., Higgins H., Latre B., Brayem B., Blondia C., Moyerman I., Salem S., Rahman Z., Kwak K. Compression testing of wireless body area networks. "Journal of Medical Systems", 36(3): 1065-1094, 2012.
2. Gonzalez S., Vasilakos A. M., Cao X., Leung, W. Body area networks: a survey. *Mobile Networks and Applications*, 16(2): 171-193, 2011.
3. Han P., Ullah S., Ullah N., Salem S., Higgins H., Kwak K. (2009) Wireless body area sensing networks for medical applications. *Magazine. Communication, Network and System Sciences*, 2: 797-803.
4. E. H. Ashraf Darwish, "Wireless Sensor Network Solutions for Wearable and Implantable Healthcare. *Monitoring, Sensors*, 2011.